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Job Design And Employee Performance In Deposit Money Banks In Anambra State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the effect of job design on employee performance in deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study were to examine the relationship between job rotation and contextual performance; job enlargement and task performance; and job reengineering and employee effectiveness in deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria. The related literature was reviewed under conceptual framework, theoretical framework, theoretical exposition and empirical review. The study was anchored on Job Characteristics Model, it adopted descriptive survey research design. The study was carried out in Anambra State, Nigeria. The population for this study comprised 1140 employees of deposit money banks in Anambra State Nigeria. The sample size of 222 employees was determined by a formula developed by Borg and Gall 1973. A structured questionnaire was designed to reflect the popular five (5) point Likert scale. Face and content validities were adopted. The reliability of the instrument was achieved through the application of test re-rest method. The research questions were analyzed using simple percentages, while hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. Findings from the study showed that there was a significant positive relationship between job rotation and task performance in deposit money banks; job reengineering has a significant positive relationship with employee effectiveness in deposit money banks and there was a significant positive relationship between job reengineering and employee turnover in deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria. The study concluded that there was a positive significant relationship between job design and employee performance in deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria. It was recommended that deposit money banks should promote rotation of jobs, in the places of work by putting in place proper mechanisms to deal with the affected employees. Proper designing and execution of job enlargement should be established so as to get better employees' capacity, resulting to improved job productivity as well as employee performance. Management of deposit money banks should appreciate redesigns of job that assist and improve performance of employees.

Keywords: Job Rotation, Job Enlargement, Job Reengineering, Contextual Performance, Task Performance; and Employee Effectiveness

INTRODUCTION

Performance is a critical factor in organizational success. Performance can be described as organizing as well as managing the causal model components that bring about the appropriate achievement of stated aims within limitations precise to an organization and to the circumstances (Lebas, 2021). An organization which is performing well is one that is achieving its goals successfully, that is to say, the one that is executing a suitable strategy effectively (Otley, 2019). The model of ability motivation` opportunity maintains performance which is a function of employees' ability motivation, opportunity to

play a part as well as capability (Appelbaum, 2023). This signifies that an institution will profit most if it arranges the process of work in such a manner that employees who are non-managerial have the chance to contribute optional effort, and this can be attained by providing in good communication, by membership of employees in self-directed and/or off-line teams and by giving them independence in decision making. Job design refers to the specification of the jobs methods, relationships and contents so as to satisfy organizational as well as technological requirements and the job holders' personal and social requirements (Armstrong, 2023). According to Ali and Aroosiya(2022) design of job is the interaction of functions of task arrangement, responsibilities and duties into an institutional work unit. Armstrong, (2023) states that design of job starts with task requirements analysis, that is what must be done, and after that it must take into consideration the following characteristics of motivation: responsibility, autonomy, self-control and finally discretion. Task is the jobs' essential and fundamental bases which ignore the actuality that jobs are planned with extremely structured relational system which influences not only interpersonal relations of employees but their associations too (Grant, 2017). Tanner (2018) reported that leaders of businesses at all times motivate individuals that they must follow a work design which is collaborative in which they ensure that workers must be accountable for their performance of work. Garg and Renu,(2021) occasionally the impending bond of goals and job setting could assist to improve the performance level as well as the job design can enhance not simply the satisfaction but as well the performance worth too. Job design is work arrangement or re rearrangement aimed at reducing and overcoming job dissatisfaction and employee alienation arising from repetitive tasks. Job design related applications started to take shapes with scientific management approach in 1990s. Fredrick Taylor is a well-known theorist about the job design, he wrote the principle of scientific management. He believed that job design identifies the duties, tasks and responsibilities of a job to be accomplished. Aim of job design is to encourage the job satisfaction and performance by changing the contents and process of a specific job so that employee may avoid from boredom. It is assumed that pay is the most significant factor at work to motivate employees. But many studies indicate that job design is the major influence on worker motivation. Therefore, management must consider how to design a job which has influence on employee motivation and performance. Three typologies of job design; job enrichment; job enlargement and job rotation have a significant relationship with employee performance. So managers should strive to understand that how the jobs are designed (Siruri & Muathe, 2021). Immense competition and increase in cost of production is becoming the reason of downsizing, lay off and restructuring so the employees of the organizations have to do a lot of work than before because now additional work is added to their duties in the form of job enlargement, enrichment and rotation (Sverke & Hellgren, 2021).

The operational merit originates from a system of human resource management that as well produces financial achievement within institutions with the aid of design of job in addition to its impending objectives a head (Huselid & Becker, 2017). Mueller, Boyer, Price and Iverson (2021) states that this is dependent on the job nature; some jobs exhibit dominant flexibility in the roles to be performed and some needed performance of role which is found extremely persistent on the other role. Besides to it, Love and Edwards, (2021) reports that design of job comprises of demands of perceived work, control of job and social support which result to superior productivity. Professionals of human resources have revealed that there is a strong job design relationship on the motivation and productivity and employees' job satisfaction within an institution.

Appropriate designing of roles as well as jobs is extremely vital in uplifting the employees' performance, which is tackled via the model of job characteristics, which describes more particularly on the job design of an individual; it as well identifies five major dimensions that include variety of skill, identity of task, and significance of task, feedback and autonomy. Design of job has several techniques: job enlargement, work autonomy, job simplification and job enrichment. Durai (2020) defines work autonomy as a system that permits workers to rotate from one job to another in a prearranged manner. Work autonomy is said to be a role of learning within organizations as workers get an opportunity to achieve a variety of job as well as varying roles (Meyer, 2021). Rotation of job is as well recognized as a practical aggrandizes and approach job associated tasks. This explains why rotation of job is planned within the phase of job

training since it confirms useful whilst moving workers from one job to another so as to discover more as well as enhance their knowledge by conducting a range of tasks. Consequently employees efficiency rise and it impacts positively to the employees' performance. According to Durai, (2020) task variety refers to the transformation of the jobs to comprise additional and/or dissimilar responsibilities. Enlargement of job refers to the different jobs combination and addition of associated responsibilities to work. Herzberg 1966, Hackman and Oldham, (1980) reported that enlargement of job is stimulated by several motivational job design mode is chiefly built on psychology.

These job design models confer about attitudes related to job such as autonomy, significance of task and variety. Enlargement of job widens scope of job, and the worker carries out numerous different responsibilities in her/his work. Durai (2020) states that job enrichment refers to the work development practices which motivate as well as challenge workers to execute their responsibilities better. Herzberg and his intention of companions were to raise satisfaction of employees at place of work with respect to job allocated to them and as well to encourage workers concerning their allocated tasks. Enrichment of job was presented by Frederick Herzberg in 1950s who was an American psychologist. The essential motive of this thought was to encourage workers through provision of those opportunities of using their capabilities in order that employees' performance as well as productivity goes up and impacts positively the environment. Enrichment of job increases depth of job, the level to which workers can plan as well as manage the task involved in their occupations.

Statement of the Problem

There has been a great concern among the deposit money banks' employees within Nigeria on the level of job design by their employers. Majority of the employees in deposit money banks are not enjoying the new jobs environments.. Poor dimensions of job design by management has been the major problem affecting employees' performance in deposit money banks. Most of workers have been compelled to work in the same task year in year out. A poorly designed job leads to a failure in getting the work on time and in a competent manner. It also discourages and makes employees dissatisfied on the job; even if the employees are competent, efficient and productive, they get disappointed, disillusioned and frustrated by poorly designed jobs. Deposit money banks have concentrated their efforts in recruiting cheap and readily available fresh graduates who switch jobs when opportunities arise as a result of poor work flow, autonomy and work practice. Lack of rotation of job reduce employee performance, in a recent survey of their client group, revealed that 68 percent of the responded agreed. Poor job design (job rotation, job enrichment, job enlargement, job reengineering and job simplification lead to poor performance which result to employees demotivation including; remuneration, team spirit and job enrichment.

There is slight if any on the effect of job design on employee performance in the developing economies. Thus, there is indeed a gap which this study seeks to fill. This research seeks to investigate the relationship between job design and employee performance of deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The study's general objective is to examine the relationship between job design and employee performance of deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria. The specific objectives sought to:

- i. Evaluate the relationship between job rotation and task performance of deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria.
- ii. Establish the correlation between job enlargement and contextual performance of deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria.
- iii. Investigate the correlation between job reengineering and employee effectiveness in in deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

This study focused on addressing the following research questions:

- i. To what extent does job rotation relate with task performance of deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria?

- ii To what level does job enlargement correlate with contextual performance of deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria?
- iii. To what level does job reengineering relate with employee effectiveness of deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses are stated in null form.

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between job rotation and task performance of deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Ho₂: Job enlargement has no significant relationship with contextual performance of deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Ho₃: Job reengineering has no significant relationship with employee effectiveness of deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

Job Design

From a conceptual perspective, job design is defined as determining the specific job content, the methods used at work and the relationships between jobs to correspond the firm's technological and organizational and the employees' social and personal expectations (Kaymaz, 2020). Job design is the functions of arranging tasks, duties, and responsibilities into an organizational unit of work (Manuaba & Darma, 2021). According to Ali & Aroosiya (2021), the working definition for the study purpose is that job design is the way to organize the contents, methods, and relationship of jobs to achieve organizational goals and objectives as well as the satisfaction of jobholders. Skill variety is the extent to which the job requires the employee to draw from a number of different skills and abilities as well as on a range of knowledge (Ajgaonkar et al., 2022). It is the methods, relationship and contents of jobs so as to satisfy requirements of organizational, technological and social requirements (Goncalves 2021). In fact, in the early job design research, companies were only focused on job simplification in order to require less skilled and cheaper workforce, assuring the elimination of all unnecessary movement to execute a particular task, in order to achieve the most efficient ways of performing work activities (Malkanthi & Hussain 2016). However, due to several reasons like technological revolution and changes of organizational demands, nowadays companies are designing and applying different kinds of work organization such as working in teams rather than individually and increasing the challenge inherent in every job.

According to Ajgaonkar et al., (2022) task significance involves importance of the task. Task significance is the degree to which a job has substantial impact on the lives of other people either in the immediate organization or external environment. Job design is the division of work tasks assigned to an individual in an organization that specifies what the worker does, how, and why. Effective job design contributes to the achievement of organizational objectives, motivation, and employee satisfaction. One of the most well-known approaches to job design is the Job Characteristics Model (Hackman & Oldham, 1975). Job design is in fact a combination of job content and the work method which has been adopted in the performance of the job (Durai, 2020). Job design is the functions of arranging task, duties and responsibilities in to an organizational unit of work (Ali & Aroosiya, 2022). Job design should start with an analysis of task requirements, namely what should be done, and then it should take into account the following motivating characteristics: autonomy, responsibility, discretion, and finally self-control (Armstrong, 2023). Chaneta (2021) defines job design as "the specification of the content, methods and relationship of jobs in order to satisfy technological and organizational requirements as well as the social and personal requirements of the job holder. Chaneta (2021) states the criteria that should be taken under consideration for job design, which are the following: Maximize the degree of specializing; minimize the time required to do the job; minimize the level of skill required; minimize learning time/ training time; maximize the use of the machines; and minimize the degree of flexibility in the performance of the job.

Job Rotation: Job rotation refers to the periodical shifting of an employee from the existing job to another job at the same level of skill requirements. It is also known as cross training. The need for job rotation arises out of over routinized jobs, boring jobs, non-challenging jobs and jobs with poor achievement orientation (Ali 2017). If an employee is performing one aspect of the job, job rotation helps him to perform all tasks in the job. Job rotation refers to the practice of moving employees from one job to another. By rotating jobs organizations can experience significant improvements in productivity, quality, and motivation. Job rotation involves shifting a person from one job to another, so that he is able to understand and learn what each job involves (Azzam & Ahmed 2013). Workers become more competent in several jobs, know various jobs, and improve the self-image and personal growth (Al-Qahtani. & Mohammed 2021). Further, the worker becomes more valuable to the organization. On the negative side, it may not be much enthusiastic, or efficiency may not be much. Besides, jobs may not improve the relationships between tasks, while activities and objectives remain unchanged. Further training costs also rise, and it can also de-motivate intelligent and ambitious trainees who seek specific responsibilities in their chosen specialties

Job Enlargement: Job enlargement refers to making the job with a variety of tasks. In the recent past, there has been an increase in the number and variety of jobs performed by the employees in organizations. When the employee feels that the job he is currently performing is less challenging, oversimplified, lacks diversity and is less meaningful, the answer is perhaps job enlargement. Thus, Job enlargement is the horizontal expansion of jobs to include more variety of tasks within the scope of the job. For instance, if worker who is assigned to the job of counting the products, finds it boring and repetitive; the job can be enlarged by including certain tasks connected to the job (David 2017). Job enlargement offers increased skill variety to employees, as there are additional tasks to perform, and efficiency and flexibility within the job are improved. Job rotation and job enlargement strategies afford employees the opportunity to bring an increased number of skills to complete work assignments.

Job Reengineering: Job reengineering is another technique of job redesign. It refers to redesigning jobs based on feedback. Jobs are performed continuously. The reactions, level of satisfaction and contribution to the goals are evaluated continuously. There may be discrepancies in the organisational objectives, job goals and finally outcomes of the jobs. Thus, jobs should be reengineered to make them suitable to employees. Job reengineering is defined as reallocation of jobs to achieve congruence of goals of individuals and organisations. Michel Hammer (2018) defined job reengineering as the fundamental rethinking and radical redesign of business processes by application of variety of tools and techniques focusing on related customer-oriented core business process to achieve dramatic improvements in critical and contemporary measures of performance such as cost, quality, service and speed. He considered that though job reengineering can be applied to any level of management, customer oriented designing and reengineering are more important for the survival and growth of the company. Job reengineering involves use of new technology and changes in the process of work.

Employee Performance

Employee Performance is the achievement of targets of the tasks assigned to employees within a particular period of time. The success of business depends on employees performance. One of the most effective ways to increase business performance and profit is to increase the performance of employees, from the lowest levels of the organization to senior management (Aroosiya & Ali, 2019). Focusing on enhancing employee performance therefore becomes the major strategy to accomplishing organization goals and objectives. Most of managerial level employees' focus on monetary benefits, promotion, job satisfaction, and job design in order to enhance employee performance. (Ali & Rehman, 2021; Sarwar, Imran, Jabbar & Hannan, 2023). In the view of Putterill and Rohrer (1995) job performance is defined as it focuses directly on employee productivity by assessing the number of units of acceptable quality produced by an employee in a manufacturing environment, within a specific time period. The success of business depends on employee' performance.

Employee performance is the contribution of employees for the achievement of organizational objective. Employees are expected to perform at an acceptable level of the set standard, and managers follow up,

and evaluate the performance of employees to attain the stated objective of an organization (Michael, 2019). Sinha (2021) stated that employees' performance depends on the willingness and openness of the employees in doing their jobs. He also stated that this willingness and openness can increase employee productivity, which also leads to increased performance. Franco et al (2022) defined performance that relies on internal motivation but presence of internal factors such as necessary skills, intellectual capacity and resources to do the job clearly have an impact. As a consequence, employers are supposed to provide appropriate working conditions in order to make sure the performance of employees meet the required standards. Stup (2023) also explained that to have a standard performance, employers have to get the employees task to be done on track as to achieve the organization goal or target.

Task Performance: Task performance can be defined as the effectiveness with which an employee performs activities that contribute to the organization's technical core, either directly by implementing a part of its technological process, or indirectly by providing it with needed materials or services (Borman and Motowidlo, 2013). Task performance is measured as response time, or it could be measured as accuracy. Task performance is a term for quantifying someone's performance on a task. It is an understanding under contractual terms between an employer and an employee or a manager and a subordinate to perform an assigned task (Pradhan & Jena, 2016). Task performance can be defined as an employee's fulfillment of the duties and responsibilities of the relevant role in the job description (Van Dyne et al., 2021) and depends on the employee's efficiency to fulfill the duties and responsibilities. In other words, it is about how effectively and efficiently the employees fulfill their responsibilities. Hence, employees' task performance contributes directly or indirectly to all company activities, including production and the efficiency and productivity of the company (Van Scotter, 2021). From the employee's perspective, task performance refers to actions that are "expected, evaluated and rewarded" (Leung, 2017). While professional competence, clear job descriptions, a suitable working environment, and moral qualities are important for high task performance, a precise and reliable job description will increase (Gül, 2023), and an unclear job description will decrease the quality of the performance assessment (Kılıç, 2016). Employees always have a perception of their performance. However, they not only fulfill the tasks specified in their key performance indicators but also many different tasks within the organization during the day, and most of them are not specified in the key performance indicators. Therefore, employees perceive two different task performances: general and specific task performance (Aslan et al., 2021).

Contextual Performance: Job performance has generally been defined as the degree to which an individual helps the organization achieve its goals. A two-factor theory of job performance consisting of task performance and contextual performance has been established by Borman and Motowidlo (2017). When employees use technical skills and knowledge to produce goods or services or accomplish a specialized task that supports the actual functions of an organization, the employees are said to be involved in task performance. Employees' engage in contextual performance when they are for instance involved with voluntarily helping colleagues, putting in extra effort to complete a given task, putting in extra hours to get work done on time and so forth (Van Scotter, 2020). Edwards, Bell, Arthur and Decuir (2018) propose that employees who are less satisfied with their jobs may exhibit lower levels of contextual performance behaviours and are therefore less likely to engage in such contextual performance activities, thus concluding that overall job satisfaction will have a stronger relationship with contextual performance than with task performance.

Adaptive Performance: Adaptive performance refers to employees' capabilities to adapt to rapidly changing work situations (Neal & Hesketh, 2019), and it is thought to include dimensions of problem solving, dealing with uncertainty, learning new tasks and procedures, and interpersonal, cultural and physical adaptability (Pulakos et al., 2020). Adaptive performance has been distinguished from task proficiency and proactivity (Griffin et al., 2017), with the former describing behaviours that are not formalized nor embedded within a social context, and the latter with anticipatory, self-directed behaviours intended to achieve desired outcomes

The concept of adaptive performance is defined in general terms as an individual's ability to adapt to dynamic work situations (Hesketh & Neal, 2019). Employees demonstrate adaptive performance by

adjusting their behaviours to the requirements of work situations and new events (Pulakos et al., 2020). Though others have highlighted the importance of a variety of adaptive behaviours (Allworth & Hesketh, 2016; Hesketh & Neal, 2019; Hollenbeck, LePine, & Ilgen, 2016; London & Mone, 2019; Murphy & Jackson, 2019), Pulakos et al. (2020) were the first to propose a global model of adaptive performance. In a first step, they reviewed research on individual performance and adaptability to changes. Then they analyzed 1,000 critical incidents (reflective of new work situations requiring a behavioural adjustment on the part of participants) involving 24 jobs in the army.

Theoretical Review

The study is guided by Job Characteristics Model. The Model of job characteristics was developed by Hackman and contemporaries, and it is majored on five jobs structural characteristics. The jobs structural characteristics included variety of task, feedback, autonomy, identity and significance. The researchers disputed that such characteristics can improve amongst others, motivation of work, satisfaction of job, and performance of job (Hackman & Oldham, 1980; Hackman & Lawler, 1971). In its early stages, the researchers had a condition on a variety of its features.

For instance, Aldag, Barr and Brief, (2021) reported that there existed weak relations concerns between characteristics of job and job performance and with additional questions over the build between job perceptions, nature as well as attitudes of job. In line with the model, a member of staff will have internal motivation which is high if three significant states of emotion are experienced. The states which can be perceived as work place motivation precursors includes; work meaningfulness, Knowledge of the job results and Responsibility for the work outcomes. In order to attain the three basic states of emotion, the model of Job Characteristics supports that the job be designed with adequate five chief characteristics of job levels. The characteristics include; variety of skill, identity of task, significance of task, feedback and autonomy. Out of the five characteristics of job, identity of task, variety of skill and significance of task are chief contributors to experienced work meaningfulness (Dodd, 2022).

It has been reported that it would be hard to find all the three characteristics of job at critical and high levels in a given job (Hackman & Oldham, 1980). Nevertheless, the same researchers dispute that levels that are high on any one of the characteristics can alone add to superior knowledgeable meaningfulness at work and therefore by extension result to satisfaction of job (Loher, 2021). The researcher will dispute that the fourth characteristic of job within the model, that is autonomy, is a vital contributor to experienced accountability for outcomes of work.

Relevance of the theory to this study in regard to this study, managers in different money deposit banks branches should come up with new ideas of job design, using the different channels of job design to innovative employee performance (Borman, 2021). In addition, Jawaharlal, (2021) states that in order to achieve the planned target, employees should be motivated, given variety of tasks, with autonomous jobs and feedback sought from them frequently to assess their performance level. Realization of the each essential decision by the top officials of deposit money banks must incorporate the employees at the lower levels.

Empirical Review

Abdul-Razak, Bernard, Kwame, and Sam-Mensah, (2022) examined the mediating roles of job satisfaction and organizational commitment in the nexus between work autonomy practices and employee performance. The study adopted a cross-sectional survey approach and obtained data through questionnaires from 122 administrative staff of the University of Education, Winneba. The Partial Least Squares, Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) approach was used to test the study's proposed model. The results supported the proposed model, showing that organizational commitment and job satisfaction are partial mediators in the relationship between work autonomy practices and employees' performance. The findings suggest that management must ensure that employees are satisfied and committed to the Work autonomy practices in order to enhance their performance. Thus, Work autonomy

practices must provide the climate that encourages career growth and development and fosters creativity in employees and not just as a routine practice or a means of punishment.

Soenanta, Akbar and Sariwulan (2021) examined the effect of job design on organizational commitment to employee retention in a lighting company. The objective of this research was to study the effect of job design and organizational commitment on employee retention in a lighting company.. The sample size for the research was 204 employees selected randomly. The data were obtained by distributing a questionnaire and analyzed by using path analysis. The result of the research concluded that: job design and organizational commitment had a positive direct effect on employee retention; job design had a positive direct effect on organizational commitment. The implication is that weak or strong retention needs to be considered in company management because it will have an impact on the tendency or resilience of employee turnover.

Shilki and Arshia (2021) examined the effect of job design and ergonomics on employee performance in Indian Automotive Sector. Growing competition and the increasing need for adaptability often require organizations to switch and convert themselves according to the demand of circumstances. In this process of reformation, employee performance gets affected by many aspects. Aiming at connecting two broad occupational concepts the article analyzed and tested the effect of job design and ergonomics on employee performance and the relatedness of job design and ergonomics. The research was conducted in 32 organizations, having managers and supervisors at about 64 categories of designations handling teams of workers in the manufacturing units of the automotive sector of India. This quantitative study, based on a sample collected through 5 points Likert scale questionnaire, was analysed using Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), correlation, and multivariate regression analysis. The results manifested that CFA model and regression analysis described a significant impact of job design and ergonomics on employee performance. The correlation outcomes revealed that job design and ergonomics were well connected having p -value of .00, $p < .005$. The findings suggested, while focusing on improving the employee upshot, it becomes necessary for organizations to include Ergonomics in Job Design as a Design for Safety.

Gabriel and Awusa (2021) determined the relationship between job design and employee turnover in Nigeria Port Authority, Rivers State. The population of the study was 409 employees of the two NPA branches in Rivers State while its sample size was 202 as established using Taro Yamene. The study adopted the cross sectional survey design in its assessment of the relationship between the variables, as such; primary data were quantitative in nature and were obtained using the structured questionnaire. The analysis comprised of the use of both descriptive and inferential statistical methods. The descriptive statistics for the demographic and univariate levels of analyses were carried out using simple percentage, frequencies and measures of central tendencies (mean) while the inferential was done with Spearman technique. The findings indicated that there was a reliable relationship between job design and the measures of employee turnover (involuntary quits and resignation). Given this outcome, the study concluded that effective job design is an antidote to employee turnover. It recommended that management of NPA should understand that the manner in which its jobs are structured or designed will either aid the firm to attract and retain reliable employees or creates an imbalance work-life that may lead to employee involuntary quits and resignation, hence caution should be exercised doing this.

Tansuria (2020). Lecturer Perception on Job Design: The Case of a Private Higher Education Institution in Indonesia. The purpose of this research was to identify the elements of the motivational job-design approach that have contributed to the lecturers' motivation while working in a private higher education institution in Indonesia. This research used descriptive statistics analysis to provide a simple summary about the perception of job design. Independent sample t-test as well as one-way ANOVA were used to investigate whether there is a difference between the demographic factors of the respondents (age, gender, and latest degree attainment) toward perception of job design. The overall result shows that lecturers' perception on the job design are "very good" (the mean score is 3.91), where the highest average scores was found on the elements such as ability/skill-level, ability/skill variety, and growth/learning (mean score are 4.55, 4.29, and 4.23 respectively, or "excellent"). On the other hand, this research also found

that among the 18 elements of motivational job-design approach, extrinsic job feedback had the lowest mean (mean score is 3.26 or “good”) which was very little in contribution to the lecturers’ motivation. This element must get priority from the institution to be addressed so that lecturers’ motivation can be improved in the future.

Disanayaka and Bandara (2020) examined the impact of job design on managerial employees’ performance in apparel sector in Matale district. A structured questionnaire was used to measure the dependent and independent variables total of 70 managerial employees were selected from garment factories in Matale district. Results of the study were analyzed using the univariate, bivariate and multivariate analysis and they revealed that there was significant positive impact on job design on employee performance. Results indicated that there is a significant positive impact of skill variety on job performance, task identity and job performance, task significance and job performance and feedback and job performance. Hence it come to the conclusion that managerial employees job performance depended on their job design. Furthermore, R2 indicated that 61.8% variance of employee performance was explained by independents variables. (skill variety, task identity, task significance, feedback) The study suggested that improving job design factors to upgrade employee performance is essential.

Tehmina, Muhammad, Muhammad & Imtiaz (2019) presented theoretical and empirical underpinnings between job design and employees’ work motivation in the banking sector of Multan city, Pakistan. The study adopted a cross-sectional survey research design in which 362 employees participated through simple random sampling technique. The findings of the study revealed that female employees were more motivated towards their jobs than male employees. Moreover, job characteristics and Work autonomy are high among senior banks employees having experience greater than 12 years. The study concluded that job enrichment was the highest influential factor in determining employees work motivation while quality of work life negatively influenced their enthusiasm level towards job. In the wake of new technological transformations, academic insight into the current work would further guide the policy makers for designing the jobs for banking sector through decentralization of managerial powers, changing in accordance with the global trends, as well as applying autonomous, mastery oriented and purposely directed policies.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed descriptive survey research design. Strauss and Corbin (2021) defined a descriptive research as a practice of gathering data so as to answer questions or test hypotheses relating to the present subject’s status in research. It involves formulating the objectives of the study, crafting the data collection methods, picking the sample, collection of data as well as analyzing the results. This study was carried out in Anambra State. Anambra is a state in southeastern part of Nigeria. Anambra is a state with a rich culture. It’s known for its great myths, giant strides, creative, hardworking and innovative people. Its history is as mythical as its great people, as there are diverse perspectives to the origin of Ndi Anambra..Primary data was employed for the study. Primary data is the data which is collected by a researcher for the specific research purpose. This study made use of questionnaire to generate the primary data. The population the study comprised 1140 employees of Deposit Money Banks in Anambra State, Nigeria. The researcher decided to study the employees of all the branches of the deposit money banks in four cities in Anambra State. The population comprised of the employees and management of the Deposit Money Banks. The choice of the deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria was based on the location, operation and their capital base recognized by Central Banks of Nigeria. A sample size of 222 employees of deposit money banks in Anambra State were driven using statistical formula devised by Borg and Gall (1973). The researcher made use of a structured questionnaire. In the structured questionnaire, participants were required to respond to options which range from Strongly Agree (5), Agree (4), Undecided (3), Disagree (2) Strongly Disagree (1). The research instrument was questionnaire, which was subjected to face and content validity procedures. The reliability of the questionnaire was established through the test- retest method and Cronbach Alpha. Reliability Coefficient and 0.94 was obtained. This was considered high enough to make the instrument reliable. The analysis of data was

performed using statistical package for the social sciences, (SPSS). Simple percentage was employed to answer the research questions. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient Efficient Analysis was used in testing hypotheses. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was adopted because they are used to measuring significance relationships between variables which makes used of correlation analysis. All tests were conducted at 0.05 level of significance.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

The researcher distributed 222 copies of the questionnaire to the respondents randomly selected. 212 were properly filled and found relevant for the study while the remaining 10 questionnaires were not properly filled by the respondents. This shows a response rate of 95.5 percent. The tables and analysis presented below covers the research questions of this research.

Research Question One: *To what extent does job rotation relate with task performance in deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria?*

Table 1: Respondents’ opinion on whether job rotation relates with task performance

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	87	41.1
Agree	92	43.4
Undecided	9	4.2
Disagree	14	6.6
Strongly Disagree	10	4.7
Total	212	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The table above showed that 41.1% of the respondents strongly agree that job rotation relate with task performance, 43.4% of the respondents agree, 4.2% were undecided, 6.6% disagreed while the remaining 4.7% disagreed.

Research Question Two: *To what level does job enlargement correlate with contextual performance in deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria?*

Table 2: Respondents view on whether job enlargement correlate with contextual performance

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	106	50
Agree	101	47.6
Undecided	0	0
Disagree	3	1.4
Strongly Disagree	2	1.0
Total	212	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 2 indicates that 50% of the respondents strongly agreed that job enlargement correlate with contextual performance, 47.6% agreed, 0% were neutral, 1.4% disagreed while 1.0% strongly disagreed.

Research Question Three: *To what level does job reengineering relate with employee effectiveness in in deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria?*

Table 3 Respondents' views on whether job reengineering relate with employee effectiveness

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	106	50.0
Agree	82	38.7
Undecided	9	4.3
Disagree	4	1.8
Strongly Disagree	11	5.2
Total	212	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The table above shows that 50% of the respondents strongly agreed that job reengineering enables employees to use resources and materials to improve their performance, 1.8% disagreed while 5.2% strongly disagreed.

Test of Hypotheses

Test of Hypothesis One

Ho: There is no significant relationship between job rotation and task performance in deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between job rotation and task performance in deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Table 4: Correlation between job rotation and task performance

		Job Rotation	Task performance
Task performance	Pearson Correlation	1	.075**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	212	212
Job Rotation	Pearson Correlation	.075	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	212	212

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 4 presents result of Pearson Product Moment Correlation test on the relationship between Job rotation and task performance. The correlation table revealed that job rotation had a correlation value of 0.075 with p-value of 0.000 is lesser than 0.05 level of significance. Since, p-value of 0.000 < 0.05 level of significance, the study rejected the null hypothesis that state that there is no significant relationship between job rotation and task performance in deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria and accepted the alternate hypothesis that there is a significant relationship between job rotation and task performance in deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Test of Hypothesis Two

Ho: Job enlargement has no significant relationship with contextual performance in deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria.

H₁: Job enlargement has a significant relationship with contextual performance in deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Table 5: Correlation between Job enrichment and contextual performance

		Job Enlargement	Contextual Performance
Contextual Performance	Pearson Correlation	1	-.086**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	212	212
Contextual Performance	Pearson Correlation	-.086	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	212	212

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 5 presents result of Pearson Product Moment Correlation test on the relationship between Job enlargement and contextual performance. The correlation table revealed Job enlargement had a correlation value -.086 and p-value of 0.000 < 0.05 level of significance. Since, p-value of 0.000 < 0.05 level of significance, the study accepted the null hypothesis that Job enlargement has no significant relationship with contextual performance in deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria and rejected the alternate hypothesis which state that Job enlargement has a significant relationship with contextual performance in deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Test of Hypothesis Three

Ho: Job reengineering has no significant relationship with employee effectiveness in deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria.

H₁: Job reengineering has no significant relationship with employee effectiveness in deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Table 6: Correlation between Job reengineering and employee effectiveness

		Job Reengineering	Employee Effectiveness
Employee Effectiveness	Pearson Correlation	1	.082**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	212	212
Job Reengineering	Pearson Correlation	.082	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	212	212

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Decision Rule

Table 6 presents result of Pearson Product Moment Correlation test on the relationship between job reengineering and employee effectiveness. The correlation table revealed Job enrichment had a correlation value .082 and p-value of 0.000 < 0.05 level of significance. Since, p-value of 0.000 < 0.01 level of significance, the study rejected the null hypothesis that state that job reengineering has no significant relationship with employee effectiveness in deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria and accepted the alternate hypothesis that stated that job reengineering has no significant relationship with employee effectiveness in deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Summary of Findings

1. There is a significant positive relationship between job rotation and task performance in deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria. Job rotation had a correlation value of 0.075 with p-value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05 level of significance.
2. Job enlargement has a significant negative relationship with contextual performance in deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria. Job enrichment had a negative correlation value -.086 and p-value of 0.000 < 0.05 level of significance.
3. Job reengineering has a significant positive relationship with employee effectiveness in deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria. Job enrichment had a correlation value 0.082 and p-value of 0.000 < 0.05 level of significance.

CONCLUSION

This work investigated the relationship between job design and employee performance in deposit money banks. Data were sourced from primary sources, and were analyzed using Pearson Moment Correlation Analysis, there was a positive significant relationship between job rotation and task performance in deposit money banks ; Job enlargement had a positive significant relationship with contextual performance, and Job reengineering had a significant relationship with employee effectiveness in deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria.. The concluded that there was a positive significant relationship between job design and employee performance in deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria,

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Deposit money banks and other organizations in Nigeria should promote rotation of job in their place of work by putting in place proper mechanisms to deal with the affected employees.
2. Proper designing and execution of job enlargement should be established so as to get better employees' capacity, resulting to improved job productivity as well as employee performance
3. Management of deposit money banks should appreciate redesigns of job that assist and improve performance of employees

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